

The Research Data Culture Conversation

Summary of the Challenge

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1 Executive Summary

Research intensive universities need a sustainable and effective approach to research data. This involves a culture change in relation to data, and the practice of data management, at an all-of-university and all-of-research sector scale.

In addition, a digital environment is needed, where automation is informed by the development, adoption and deployment of an RDMP-2.0 standard - which is researcher-led and community-driven.

In implementation we seek metadata-driven and machine-actioned management practices which capture the context of data sufficiently well to support most life-cycle decisions to be made about those data.

The broad goals proposed are as follows.

- The right people have access to the right data for the right amount of time, using systems that acknowledge changes of stewardship and achieve long term preservation.
- The systems deliver a continuous reduction in the cost of making decisions about data and data life cycles and thereby reducing the human effort required in data curation.
- A cultural change occurs in which researchers acknowledge and articulate the kind of data that have end-of-life events and institutions implement those end-of-life events.
- A resource aware practice develops where data naturally migrates towards lower cost but also increasingly compliant retention solutions.

This project is supported by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC). The ARDC is enabled by NCRIS.

2 Background

Research intensive universities are working together to articulate the nature of a sustainable and effective research data culture, under the banner of the Research Data Culture Conversation (RDCC).

The context comes from:

- measured data growth of 75% per year over the last 15 years at a major Australian University; and
- the observation of data growth rates, such as in genomics and imaging, which can be much higher.

Some key properties of the situation are as follows:

- A. Institutions will increasingly coordinate and invest in large-scale infrastructure to support the growth in the creation and use of research data and to ensure policy compliance on retention, access and disposal.
- B. The efficient use of such infrastructure depends on information and metadata not readily and systematically available, and that increasing the availability of such metadata depends on the appropriate involvement of researchers.
- C. Research data life cycles span areas of interest and activities traditionally owned by multiple research support pillars, including the library, records, archive and IT functions of universities, and more recently eResearch functions.
- D. Opportunities to gain efficiencies, economies of scale and quality improvements, all require coordinated action by these pillars in relation to each researcher's data and research data overall.
- E. Improved alignment is also needed between institutions, research funders and other third parties, such as those created by national infrastructure investment in data.

Those universities that are facing the problem at scale want to work with all universities to accelerate a change in practice and to enable research communities as a whole to 'buy in' to the treatment of their research data.

Improving the systematic management of research data is expected to be a journey, because:

- Adoption will occur at different rates in different institutions;
- The goals and approaches will evolve as understanding improves; and
- Different beneficiaries will have different interests in the gains provided.

Multiple meetings held across the last two years have confirmed a growing interest in addressing the challenge. A strong agreement about the current paradox in research data management practice exists, as follows.

Research Data Management Plans (RDMPs, as researcher provided information) created at research initiation are not used to inform subsequent decision making.

The contrary would be expected. The continuous improvement of a 'container of information around data, about that data', targeting the capture of value from that data over the course of its lifetime, must be able to inform the decision making required by that data's life cycles.

An RDMP-2.0 process is envisaged, whereby research data management would transition from a plan (waterfall) based approach to a continuous improvement-based approach.

The RDMP-2.0 process would:

- Translate best practice improvements arising from institutional efforts into common national practice by coordinating aligned activities;
- Realise FAIR principles for data management through the harmonisation of metadata and improving the coherence of the multiple systems supporting access to that data; and
- Improve efficiency and compliance within support “pillars” (archives, data privacy, eResearch, ethics, IT, library, records, the research office and security):
 - By using a machine-driven approach which leverages common metadata to inform better data management decisions as data progresses through its life cycles; and
 - By providing actionable reporting relating cost to benefit.

A simplified summary was developed during the consultations, in which the main institutional data challenges are seen to have both Yin and Yang dimensions.

The diagram below summarises that key finding: Data management goals and practice need to encompass Preservation, Sharing and Re-use **as well as** Resourcing, Sensitivity and End-of-Life, if research institutions and research communities are to more effectively manage research data.

3 Principles

The consultations have been deliberately practitioner focussed, in order to elicit learnings and understandings from current efforts by institutions to respond to their data challenges.

The steering group has extracted the following key points from the discussions. To be successful, improvements to Data Practice should:

- Be research-domain focused
- Be researcher centric and assist research
- Be efficient and add institutional value
- Be implementable across and within institutions

Be research-domain focused

Research domains need to lead the data management rules for their data, agree their metadata and develop an understanding of the value data retention holds to them.

Different research domains can have different life cycles, retention periods and metadata.

Large Research Institutions will host multiple domains or disciplines and must seek efficiencies in 'horizontal' services that support many of them.

Be researcher centric and assist research

Have low / no effort to perform and low barriers to entry.

Motivate the researcher to contribute, on research terms, adding value to attribution and recognition.

Tolerate and enable researchers doing something new / not well understood.

Be efficient and enabling for the majority of researchers while supporting individual curation if needed.

Be efficient and add institutional value

Leverage international, national, domain and cross-institutional platforms and capabilities where possible.

Capture data well from the outset, prioritise retention of data with value and minimise duplication.

Automate where possible and reduce / limit the human capital required to achieve the goals.

Report and track cost, utilisation and citation.

Be implementable across and within institutions

Focus on the P-Dimension (People - Policy - Process) and best practice within these dimensions first before focusing on the T-dimension (Tools - Technology - Transformation).

Engage with a critical mass of research intensive institutions.

Involve all institutional research support "pillars" including: archives, eResearch, library, IT, records and the research office.

Support the sharing and movement of data and associated metadata between pillars and across institutions and over time.

In all the above, a large number of entities need to be engaged. Existing cooperative arrangements and especially those that engage research communities and their data, should be involved. New consultation arrangements should only be created where none are present.

4 Emerging Themes

There are many unknowns and a significant overall complexity to the research data challenge that need to be taken into account. The transition from a waterfall-based plan approach to a continuous improvement approach is essential.

Unknowns	<p>What are the key decisions that need to be made, or what events occur, that cause data to have a life cycle?</p> <p>What changes can be made that reduce or remove the labour cost associated with knowing those decisions or events occurred and acting on them?</p> <p>How can those decisions or events be used to assign data most cost effectively across services with different access, curation and cost (tiers of storage)?</p>
Process	<p>It is impossible to predict where commonality will exist and where differentiation matters most. Therefore, the concept is to take a 'data source by data source' and 'research community by research community' approach rather than attempting to directly postulate an encompassing generality.</p>

The RDMP-2.0 should be developed as follows:

- Start with a small number of communities that can describe the decisions around data that cause data to have a life cycle, and have experience with the trade offs in tiering.
- Generate worked-through examples that can guide less experienced groups that follow.
- Frame the activity into requirements (community by community) and into best practice responses (institution by institution or NCRIS capability by capability).
- Undertake coordination activities to align implementations in their visible functionality, and create a standard around that visible functionality (the new RDMP-2.0)

Significant leadership around requirements and best practice responses which must be accessed will exist outside of the universities. For example, the identification of commonalities in data life cycles has already proven powerful in national research infrastructure investments such as AURIN, IMOS, AUScope, TERN, BPA and others.

The means for making improvements would need to be developed in a further planning process. Some indicative concepts are set out below.

1) Research data practice

Improvement is dependent on the implementation of systems/processes in institutions and between institutions. This is very dependent on institutional and all pillars involvement. The showbag activity started by the RDCC is helpful to this.

Dimensioning and then measuring current state

- Over time delivering trends and hot spots etc

This is a repetitive ongoing activity

Implementation of information capture around data

- Enabling smart decision making in all the pillars that support research data management within a university

This is likely to be a bespoke activity dependant on organisational structures, information systems and technologies in place specific to each university

Architecting a data migration framework (that meets policy and access realities)

- Where duplication is reduced, more data is held on lower cost solutions and in which the business case for low durability options can be determined

This is a collaborative activity aimed at creating a common framework that does apply to the more bespoke systems in each university

2) Research data purpose

Improvement is dependent on the knowledge and capabilities of researchers. We need to define more effective life cycle concepts and community agreements around them. This is work that needs to be carried forward with the participation of researchers and domain specific data investments.

Articulation of 'normal practice' in different data life cycles

- Starting with a small number of exemplary data streams, identify life cycle transitions and associated changes in access, durability and use, broadening to an increasing variety and volume and complexity of data over time
- Data stream selection could be arranged to ensure a spread exists across FOR codes, data sources, scales of data produced, and reuse potential and data streams related to RDSI supported collections can be included

This is a stepwise refinement activity on a research domain by domain, or research discipline by discipline basis. It must be expected that some learnings in specific cases can have broad value across many other cases

Maturing of Smart Decision Making in research data management

- Articulating statements of functionality, extracted from bespoke implementations, to create technology independent guidelines and how-to's for decision making automation

This is a knowledge capture, encoding and dissemination process, which builds a stock of knowledge regarding effective and affordable practice in research data management.

3) Research data investment

Improvement is dependent on the perceived value of research data. We need to understand the measures and decisions required in assigning value, clarify the goals of research data management with respect to the value and cost of data, and cross-inform and connect 1, and 2.

Development of RDMP-2.0

- Identify or develop reference implementations of components of RDMP-2.0.
- Develop implementation and practitioner guidelines
- Establish compliance expectations and standards for RDM processes in universities.

This is a collaborative standards development process

Many government policy, university and national infrastructure goals could be advanced. For example: improved research integrity; more certain access to data underpinning published research, university held prestige collections, the flow of data into science agency collections and support for the data life cycles associated with data in all of the NCRIS capabilities.

An overall summary of the themes clustering around the development of the RDMP-2.0 is depicted below.

5 Consultation Phases

The journey so far...

Since 2018, the RDCC has engaged over 105 participants across 34 institutions and organisations. Each forum has seen representation from multiple institutional pillars, who gather to discuss their challenges with research data management and to discuss a collaborative approach to finding a solution. The consultations undertaken over the last 2 years is set out below.

2018 - First Meeting

Four research intensive universities (Monash University, The University of Melbourne, The University of Sydney and The University of New South Wales) met to discuss if a shared experience existed around the emerging data challenges.

2018 - eResearch Australasia Birds of Feather

A Birds of a Feather session was held in order to broaden participation and introduce the activities of RDCC. The question put to the BoF was - should we work on this together? This was agreed by those present.

2019 - National Meeting held in Sydney

Representatives from seven universities, the ARDC, the Australian Government Department for Education and Training and Universities Australia met in Sydney. This meeting confirmed the value in working together and set out the initial principles of the RDCC (see section 3).

2019 - Discussions with ARDC

Discussions around how institutional and national data infrastructure investments might add value to each other developed with the ARDC. This led to a project to investigate those linkages (see RDCC - A Development Response).

2019 - National Zoom Meetings

The project activity with the ARDC was initiated with national zoom meetings which invited participation from a broader set of institutions.

2019 - eResearch Australasia Data Summit and Birds of a Feather sessions

The ARDC Data Summit and the eResearch Australasia conference provided an important opportunity to hold two open forums on the RDCC. These were used to further articulate the research data management challenge as well as gain insight into the next steps. The Yin and Yang of data was first introduced here.

2019/2020 - Regional Meetings in Victoria, New South Wales and Queensland

Regional meetings were held to understand the strategies for the further development of the RDCC. The result of these meetings includes the emerging themes set out in this paper and the project scoping set out in the RDCC paper “A Development Response”.

6 Table of Participants

The table below captures the attendees of the meetings, we are unable to report the participants in the Data Summit and Birds of a Feather sessions.

Name	Organisational Role	Organisation
Adrian Burton	Directory	ARDC
Tom Honeyman	Data consultant (NSW)	ARDC
Michelle Barker	Director	ARDC
Keith Russell	Manager, Engagements	ARDC
Julia Martin	Research Data Consultant - NCRIS Capability	ARDC
Richard Ferrers	eResearch Research Data Analyst	ARDC
Max Wilkinson	Special Advisor - Infrastructure	ARDC
Andy White	Data Consultant	ARDC
Ian Duncan	Director, eResearch Infra and Services	ARDC
Isabelle Lys	Senior lecturer	Australian Catholic University
Kirsty Douglas	Assistant Director, Research Policy Team	Australian Government Department of Education and Training
Helen Duke	Associate Director, ICT Infrastructure - Project Delivery and Engagement, Information Technology Services	Australian National University (ANU)
Sophie Holloway	Associate Director, Research Analysis, Systems and Integrity, Research Services Division	Australian National University (ANU)
Cameron Jack	Manager ANU Bioinformatics Consultancy	Australian National University

		(ANU)
Roxanne Missingham	University Librarian	Australian National University (ANU)
Roslyn Prinsley	Head Strategic Research Initiatives - Office of the Deputy Vice Chancellor (Research & Innovation)	Australian National University (ANU)
Douglas Robertson	Director Research Services	Australian National University (ANU)
Sharyn Wragg	Manager, Research School of Biology IT - ANU College of Science	Australian National University (ANU)
Erin Gallant	Manager, Digital Scholarship	Australian National University (ANU)
Iftikhar Hayat	eResearch Project Officer	Charles Darwin University
Louise Patterton	Data Librarian	CSIR
Claire Mason	Senior Social Scientist	CSIRO
Paul Box	Social Architecture Science Lead	CSIRO
Stephanie von Gavel	Business Development Manager	CSIRO
John Brown	Librarian	Curtin University
Christopher McAvaney	eResearch Service Manager, eResearch	Deakin University
Dr Erin Morton	Manager, Health Systems Research	Flinders University
Christopher Adda	Manager, Research Infrastructure	La Trobe University
Alicia Rogers	librarian	Macquarie University
Simon O'Toole	Senior Specialist Research Systems Engineer	Macquarie University
Sarah Rickard	Manager Research Governance and Audit	Melbourne Health
Lucinda Davies	Archives Manager	Monash University (MU)
Neil Dickson	Research Infrastructure Manager	Monash University (MU)

Sandra Ennor	Senior Records Analyst	Monash University (MU)
Rhys Francis	Research Data Consultant	Monash University (MU)
David Groenewegen	Director, Research, University Library Administration	Monash University (MU)
Ali Hayes-Brady	Senior Records Analyst	Monash University (MU)
Anitha Kannan	Research Infrastructure Program Manager - Office of Vice-Provost (Research & Research Infrastructure)	Monash University (MU)
Catherine Nicholls	Records Manager	Monash University (MU)
Komathy Padmanabhan	Strategic Business Analyst	Monash University (MU)
Steve Quenette	Deputy Director, Monash eResearch Centre	Monash University (MU)
Lisa Kruesi	PhD Candidate	Monash University (MU)
Adrian Tritschler	Research Data Storage	Monash University (MU)
Neil Dickson	Manager, Research Infrastructure	Monash University (MU)
Nicholas McPhee	Research Data Management Specialist	Monash University (MU)
Gayathri St George	Senior Research Officer	Monash University (MU)
Ai-Lin Soo	Project Officer, Office of Pro-Vice Chancellor (Research and Research Infrastructure)	Monash University (MU)
Amanda	Research and Innovation Program Director	NSW Health Pathology
Jo Dalvean	eResearch Project Manager, Research Data Services	RMIT
Nicholas May	eResearch Software Developer (Research Data)	RMIT
Manuel Nielsen	Research Data Manager	South Eastern Sydney Local Health District
Krupa Krishnaprasad	Research Coordinator	St Vincent's Hospital Melbourne
Reeti Brar	Liaison Librarian	The University of Notre Dame

		Australia
Jennifer Stanton	Manager Digital Collections - Library	The University of Sydney
Anne-Marie Lansdown	Deputy Chief Executive (also Australian Research Data Commons Board Member)	Universities Australia (UA)
Chairan Keesing	Theses Coordinator	University of Canberra
Stephen Giugni	Associate Director, Research Platform Services	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Rowland Mosbergen	Petascale Campus Initiative Facilitator	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Rachel Tropea	Senior Research Archivist	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Graeme Hairsine	Associate Director, Information Governance and Engagement	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Steven Manos	Associate Director, Research Platforms	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Donna McRostie	Director, Research and Collections	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Peter Neish	Library	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Ailie Smith	Senior Research Archivist, Digital Scholarship	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Chris Stueven	Records Analyst	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Jaye Weatherburn	Data Stewardship Coordinator	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Lyle Winton	Manager, Digital Scholarship	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Gene Melzack	Data Curator	University of Melbourne (UoM)
Kylie Burgess	Research Data Lead	University of New England
Luc Betbeder-Matibet	Director, eResearch Technology	University of NSW (UNSW)
Richard Buckley	Manager, Records and Archives	University of NSW (UNSW)
Kate Carruthers	Chief Data & Insights Officer	University of NSW (UNSW)
Adrian Chew	Data Management Training Consultant	University of NSW (UNSW)

Jacky Cho	Project Officer, Office of Pro-Vice Chancellor (Research Infrastructure)	University of NSW (UNSW)
Maude Frances	Associate Director, Scholarly Communications & Repositories - UNSW Library	University of NSW (UNSW)
Hero Macdonald	Director, Digital Library Services	University of NSW (UNSW)
Jake Surman	Research Data Specialist	University of NSW (UNSW)
Lisa Conti Phillipps	Liaison Librarian	University of NSW (UNSW)
Crosby	Operations Manager	University of NSW (UNSW)
Jenny Johnston	Project Manager - UQ Research Data Manager	University of Queensland (UQ)
Cassandra Graesser	Research Data Manager - Project Officer	University of Queensland (UQ)
Paula Martinez	Research Office, National Imaging Facility	University of Queensland (UQ)
Kathleen Smeaton	Associate Director Library	University of Queensland (UQ)
David Abramson	Director, Centre for Research Computing	University of Queensland (UQ)
Siddeswara Guru	eResearch Director, Centre for Research Computing	University of Queensland (UQ)
Joe Shapter	Pro-Vice-Chancellor (Research Infrastructure)	University of Queensland (UQ)
Amberlyn Thomas	Associate Director - Learning and Research Services	University of Queensland (UQ)
Rebecca Deuble	Librarian - Research Outputs and Impact	University of Queensland (UQ)
Fei Yu	Senior librarian	University of Queensland (UQ)
Sarah Brown	Senior Manager, Research Performance	University of Queensland (UQ)
Chris Albone	Enterprise Architect, ICT	University of Sydney (USyd)
Adele Haythornthwaite	Research Data Consulting Lead Sydney Informatics Hub	University of Sydney (USyd)
Andrew Janke	Associate Director, Research Technology Strategic Engagement and Planning, ICT	University of Sydney (USyd)

Katrina McAlpine	Associate Director, Publishing and Data Services	University of Sydney (USyd)
Jennifer McLean	Manager Digital Curation and Data Services	University of Sydney (USyd)
Piyachat Ratana	Research Data Officer	University of Sydney (USyd)
Tim Robinson	Head of RM/Archives/Privacy - TBC	University of Sydney (USyd)
Ryan Sullivan	eResearch Consultant, Digital Strategy, ICT	University of Sydney (USyd)
Sharyn wise	Eresearch analyst and research data manager	University of Technology Sydney
Rebecca Cooke	Research Collections Coordinator - Library	University of the Sunshine Coast
Kate Croker	Library Manager (Research Publications and Data Services)	University of Western Australia (UWA)
Andy Lavender	Associate Director Information Governance and	University of Western Australia

	Reporting	(UWA)
Jay Guyver	Manager, Information Governance - Information Governance and Reporting - Strategy, Planning and Performance	University of Western Australia (UWA)
Debra Paisley	Records Manager	University of Western Australia (UWA)
Jason Nairnsey	Portfolio Manager - Research & Library	University of Wollongong
Anna Papoulis	Research Services Librarian	UNSW Canberra
Katrina Trewin	Research Engagement Coordinator, Metadata	Western Sydney University